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Role of CTC in Teacher Education for Community Development

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Abstract:

School is a miniature community and represents culture, ethos, rules, regulations, duties of larger community outside the school. Hence, teachers are to be oriented for all civic responsibilities and duties as a citizen of the nation for the grass root community development. This can be achieved by integrating citizenship training in teacher education curriculum in pre-service training programmes. Various activities are carried out in the five day residential camp i.e. Citizenship Training Camp (CTC), where the student-teachers are oriented towards the community, civic life and its progress. The educational cultural, physical, health and hygiene, social issues, etc, are discussed in various sessions with experts and shared with the community at large. This paper focusses all these important issues, describes few activities and suggests other along with the course of presentation.

Key Words: Teacher Education; Community Development; Citizenship Training Camps (CTC).

Introduction

Education is always being a need of the community, without education there is no scope of development of the community. In the entire human history, teachers have played a pivotal role in imparting education to the society. The role of teacher was different in Vedic, later Vedic, Buddhist, Medieval, British and Modern period. Regardless of these differences teacher had and continues to have a key role to play which was very crucial in shaping of community in general and education of children in particular. In Vedic period of education, the teacher was considered as an ideal person in the community, who was intellectually, socially, logically, spiritually and morally perfect person. Teacher gave moral and religious education and imparted values by leading a perfect example of 24x7 model in his residential school or Gurukula. However, modern the community has become today, our teachers are working lesser than 24x7, and i.e. they are working only for 8 hours or less. This means the professionalism of highest level

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is disappearing among modern day teachers. The community values were highest in olden days. In Buddhist period, indirectly teacher was playing a key role in development of community. For example, teacher was completely responsible for education, food, clothes and residence of a student monks and he had to treat the students if they fell sick. This was irrespective of disciple's caste or background and hence school had representation of the entire community that is the teacher addressed entire community's needs by being with them. During mediaeval period of education system, the aim of teacher was to train the students in such a way that they should become useful for themselves and the community. The teachers were giving theoretical as well as practical education and that was a major contribution of teacher to the community. These schools have witnessed representation from Muslim and as well as Hindu communities. The most recent example before independence was that of education of Dr. Rajendra Prasad and Raja Ram Mohan Roy etc who graduated from Madarsa background. These schools attempted to reach contemporary social values, community requirement and teachers had freedom to design their curriculum and impart education. In modern education, "moral education class" is compulsorily in the classroom and in these classes teacher trains the student to inculcate moral values for happy life in the community. However, the continuous decline and disconnect among schools and community is a cause of concern. These discussions come up repeatedly in educational deliberations. *There is a recurrent theme in educational literature connecting the teaching of history and citizenship to the promotion of national identity (Jerome & Clemitshaw, 2012).*

That is why in present situation, the teacher has a pivotal role to play in management and guidance of the community in particular. Therefore, the curriculum is modified to incorporate in school and out of school activities and school forms a miniature community. An education committee in the west has endorsed this long ago.

Activities involving experience in actual school and classroom situations and with children in normal life situations, both in school and out, should constitute important elements in the entire teacher education programme. (Education, 1941)

This leads to inclusion of activities related to the community and citizenship training within and outside the school. However, there are no proper guidelines and consensus among stakeholders, which has been emphasised by Jerome.

With no clear tradition of citizenship or citizenship education, those responsible for the recent introduction of citizenship into the National Curriculum had to tread carefully to carry the consent of politicians and educationalists (Jerome, Critical citizenship experiences? Working with trainee teachers to facilitate active citizenship in schools, 2006).

Now, the teachers are getting the opportunity of training for community development work during their pre-service training in the form of Citizenship Training Camp (CTC). The citizenship training camp (CTC) of pre service teacher education programmes provide an opportunity to know the community, where they have to initiate their professional life. These camps in Indian context, give a firsthand information about the community, social problems community mapping, social relationships, faiths and beliefs, social and political exclusion, educational status of community, civic values etc. Thus, varied experiences of civilised community are provided. Jerome summarises *three inter related strands in citizenship training, which include social and moral responsibility; political literacy; and community involvement.*

Through teacher education programme whether it be regarded as general or professional preparation of teachers, planned experiences should be provided as part of the learning process, to give students varied opportunities to come in direct contact with individuals and the community in real life situations as a basis of both training and more careful selection for teaching or other occupations in terms of personality and other significant factors. (Education, 1941)

For the convenience of this paper study, the Citizenship Training Camp (CTC) is considered as *a an inbuilt course of a pre-service training of teachers, where student-teachers are oriented about the society or community in which they live, by bringing them together in a short duration residential programme, and the programme is woven in such a way that they get firsthand information from the experts working in different fields like education, health, hygiene, non-governmental organisation, social upliftment etc. and they are also provided opportunity to interact with the community or society and their representatives.* Thus, the overall aim of the programme is to bring the student-teachers close to the society or community.

Thus, the CTC can play a pivotal role in teacher education for community development. The CTC is a well-scheduled practical activity to train the student-teachers to motivate them for community development in natural setting. Thus, it brings out various challenges which need some accommodation in student-teachers'. Jerome (2006) indicates that to develop skills of participation and responsible action,

Pupils should be taught to: (a) use their imagination to consider other people's experiences and be able to think about, express and explain views that are not their own (b) negotiate, decide and take part responsibly in both school and community-based activities (c) reflect on the process of participating.

The CTC in Action

The CTC is a five days training programme of student-teachers in which the student-teachers have to stay in a nearby rural village in a natural environment. Each day of the CTC programme is divided into 3 sessions. First session is for the fieldwork in the village, next session is for the lectures from resource persons and the last session is for the cultural programme. The aim of all the three sessions is to involve the student-teachers to understand the issues and concerns of community and to motivate them to participate in community development tasks. These three sessions are depicted pictorially in the figure 1, which indicates that the fieldwork is of utmost importance in this training camp, but at the same time importance of cultural programmes cannot be undermined.

Figure 1. Showing different activities conducted in CTC

First Session–Fieldwork in the Village

Every day the student-teachers have to follow a particular timetable according to it they have to get up early in the morning and perform Yoga, Meditation and to perform some exercises for healthy mind and fitness of the body. This is the implementation of “*a sound mind in a sound body*”. Every day in the first session student-teachers, have to perform different activities, which are depicted in figure 2, and these are to be taken only as an example, where as the organisers can devise their own programmes

Figure 2. Showing some fieldwork activities as part of CTC

1. *Fieldwork in the Village (Survey)*

The fieldwork is for the student-teachers to do a survey of the village where in they administer a questionnaire on the villagers to know about local population, education, occupation, awareness regarding education of children, family planning, health (AIDS) etc. Through this survey, the student-teachers will come to know about socio-economic conditions of the village. According to social conditions of the villagers, the student-teachers conduct the awareness programmes for them.

2. *Free Health Check-up*

The student-teachers conduct a free health check up camp for the villagers where the government doctors or internship doctors at the village government hospitals. A routine health check up like eye test, dental check up, blood check up etc. are done and if any problem or disease is found in case any of the villager then further reference is made. Apart from this free health check up, free vaccination from government hospital can also be provided to the children.

3. *Awareness Programme*

This is a very important programme where villagers are invited to gather at some particular place where they get awareness regarding health issues, family planning, education, government schemes etc. In this programme, all the student-teachers explain one after another, the importance of the above aspects in the local language, and in case of doubt, satisfactory answers are given. Apart from

these aspects, few social evils like drinking habit (alcoholism), child labour, domestic violence etc. are also discussed. The student-teachers discuss some good habits and motivate them to adapt these good habits for better life.

4. *Distribution of Items*

This is one of the important and difficult jobs, as it needs lot of patience and good behaviour and real empathetic feeling towards the community. In this activity as it's first stage the student-teachers collect old clothes, toys, books from the donors beforehand and then sort them out, give them a shape of gift. In second stage, they identify the villagers who are in very vulnerable condition and most needy. According to their needs and based on the data gathered they distribute the donors' gifts without hurting the emotions of the villagers. This activity could be optional to the student-teachers and planned systematically.

5. *Plantation*

Plants' life is very essential for our lives so we have to grow more plants. In this programme with the help of agriculture experts and farmers, the student-teachers have to plant at least one plant. These plants should be in such an area that the villagers can easily water them and take care after departing of student-teachers.

Second Session–Lectures from Resource Persons

The second session of each day is earmarked for invited guests or eminent scholars to deliver lectures on various issues related to community development. The examples of eminent scholars or resource persons by whom guest lectures can be held are depicted pictorially in figure 3.

Figure 3. Showing examples of lectures by resource persons

1. *Educational Administrative Authorities*

Educational administrative authorities like Block Education Officer (BEO), Educational Officer (EO) etc. are invited to explain the recently framed educational policies and field level practices to the student-teachers. This platform can be used to discuss their experiences in schools education to know the current situation in education system.

2. *Doctors*

Doctors explain the student-teachers various issues and problems of health and hygiene, unhygienic environment and advent of new diseases and their prevention. They discuss the importance of vaccinations to babies, regular health check up, AIDS etc. These discussions give immense knowledge regarding health to the student-teachers, which they can spread in the whole village.

3. *Local Village Authority*

Presently, three tier system of governance is being followed in India, where Gram Panchayat is available at the village level. Any local village authority like village Sarpanch can be called to discuss the issues of the village. He/she will be the right person who can explain the village conditions and the problems like remote schools, power problem, road problem, water problem apart from these various kinds of other problems can be discussed. The authority can also give information about the facilities and amenities provided by the government. These kinds of lectures can encourage the student-teachers to think about their own community and the problems faced by them which lead them to think and do something for their community apart from their regular duties.

4. *A Panel Discussion*

This is the last academic activity of the programme where experts and resource persons can be called to discuss the village problems and discuss the probable solutions, which can be conducted by inviting government officials.

After this panel discussion, a brief report of the respective village can be prepared. This could be submitted to the local bodies, Panchayati Raj institutions. A small step may bring a big change in the village. This step definitely lights a candle of the community development in the heart of prospective teachers.

Third Session–Cultural Programme

The third session of day is cultural programme, which have to be organised by the student-teachers and the local villagers can be involved in it. Following are the suggestive programmes (figure 4), which can be conducted in the cultural programmes of CTC.

Figure 4. Showing examples of Cultural Programme

1. *Drama*

There are various issues or themes on which drama can be performed like, education, midday meal, health, dowry system, drinking habits etc. The student-teachers have to select different themes write a small script and perform the drama. This activity will develop artistic and aesthetic sense of the student-teachers and some heart touching dramas will put a lifelong impact on the student-teachers.

2. *Folk songs and dance*

Villagers feeling can be understood only through their folk songs in their own dialect. These songs will show their culture and values. Few villagers can also be invited for their folk dance, which shows their talent and their feelings.

On the final day a valedictory speech from eminent personality can be conducted, certificate to the student-teachers are distributed, and this ends the CTC programme.

Influence of CTC

After finishing the camp, each student is asked to write the report of the camp. Jerome has viewed extracts of such reports after citizenship training and analysed. *A number of extracts from the student-teachers' assignments have been found out, which illustrate four lessons learned through citizenship training project viz.:* ♦ *active citizenship motivates pupils;* ♦ *small is beautiful;* ♦ *collaboration with colleagues is important;* ♦ *critical observation of colleagues can help avoid pitfalls.*

After the CTC programme, the teacher trainees develop and amass ecological dimensions that influence agricultural practices. This knowledge helps them to enrich their real life situations. This increases the relevance of education to community thereby making learning more community specific and practical life.

The teachers can design and organise their content and learning experiences from the community for the classroom.

In his study about Student-teachers and their Attitudes towards 'Race': in the context of the role of citizenship education Wilkins tried to explore the students' attitudes to 'race' issues, and discussed the implications for initial teacher education institutions as they prepare student-teachers for delivering citizenship education. He found that through building strong links with local communities to address local concerns, through placing managing for change at the centre of the school structure, incorporating the socially transformative agenda of schooling into both staff development and curriculum planning, it is possible to work even within the highly restrictive culture of education today (Wilkins, 2001).

There is a need to develop capacity of teachers with regard to identifying and contextualising the content areas and linking them for community development. These include agricultural and non-agricultural areas like folk culture including songs, festivals, fairs and games. The National Curriculum Framework for Teacher education, 2010 (NCFTE, 2010) has also given details of role of community knowledge in education. Thus, CTC tries to achieve vision of teachers and teacher education, "Teacher education programme need to broaden the curriculum (both school and teacher education) to include different traditions of knowledge; educate teachers to connect school knowledge with community knowledge and life outside the school" (NCFTE, 2010, p21). Therefore, the NCFTE (2010) advocates for courses like 'teacher and learner in society' and 'gender, school and society'. There is a need to develop community-centred model for teaching and learning based on socio-cultural aspects. This will help in sharing of common experiences, conversation, extended time activities, collaborative learning etc. All these are possible in Citizenship Training Camps (CTC). Thus, the CTC training has a great role in community development through teacher education programmes.

Conclusion

At present, the CTC programme is being conducted in various teachers training institutions of Karnataka, Kerala, and Tamil Nadu etc. After knowing the significance of the CTC programmes for Teacher Education it can be implemented in almost all teacher education institutions of India. This will become a motivating factor to the student-teachers for developing their community and help them in future to work for their community upliftment and to become good and ideal citizens of their nation. This orientation of teacher trainees in these camps give lot of ideas about community, civic rules, culture,

customs, that is basic requirement of teachers working in a particular community. Thus, it opens new vistas of community development through teacher education.

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